

Bacterial Nanocellulose, A Natural Non-Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient for Gel Design. Finding a Natural Mosquito Repellent, A Community Experience

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ABSTRACT

Bacterial Nano Cellulose (BNC) is a primary metabolite synthesized inside *Pseudomonas fluorescens* bacterial cell. BNC has distinctive characteristics that introduces modifications in its biological and physicochemical properties. Its swelling capacity under special conditions make it an unique model for semi-solid topical pharmaceutical forms design. Cleaner production studies developed in our laboratory demonstrate that it is possible to reduce the concentration of synthetic excipients in gel formulas with the addition of small concentrations of BNC. This work shows our experience in the redesign of the base formula for semi-solid gels, its implementation on the manufacture of a natural mosquito repellent, and a joint experience with a rural school and its community in Amberes-Tucuman-Argentina. The primary health care center (CAPS- Comuna de Amberes) provided alarming data regarding the prevalence of dengue virus, which is endemic in the area due to its geographical location. To the natural active pharmaceutical ingredient selection, aromatic plants from the area that contain citronellol and/or limonene in high concentrations were surveyed. *Cymbopogon citratus*, was selected, due to its abundance in the Amberes área. Safety evaluation and persistence studies of the repellent action were carried out on 100 healthy volunteers from Amberes commune.

The main objective was to design a natural mosquito repellent, suitable for all ages, sustainable, biodegradable. To ensure the success of the technological design, quality controls established by the Argentine pharmacopeia were carried out. In addition, the results of safety, organoleptic characteristics, acceptance and persistence of repellent action, were evaluated.

Since there is no foreseeable risk from the use of BNC, nor other ingredient on the repellent designed is possible and representative to evaluate the safety of their ingredients simply evaluating the appearance of edema and/or erythema (exploring potential allergies) in clinical test. This study meets the ethical and scientists standards to design, conduct, recording and reporting studies that involve the participation of human beings stipulated by the Ministry of Health of Argentina, (Resolution N° 1490/07).

The combined polymer formulation design introduced optimal characteristics in the natural mosquito repellent gel. The selection of the plant species met the desired characteristics of high concentration of terpenes from the limonene family and abundance in the study area. The pH values obtained are suitable and help to maintain skin health. The viscosity and extensibility tested in vitro are adequate, facilitating the application and persistence of the product on the skin. Studies in healthy volunteers showed absence of edema and erythema within 24 hours. No perception of skin dryness was recorded among the 100 volunteers surveyed. The persistence of the product on the skin and the repellent action was at least 3 hours in 62% of the cases. The organoleptic properties were adequate. The gel was described as soft, with a pleasant aroma, rapid absorption and a persistent refreshing sensation.

The product is suitable for use as a mosquito repellent, its design is optimal for the area where the study was carried out, due to its climatic characteristics and living conditions. It is desirable to continue the studies by expanding the number of healthy volunteers and the area of influence of the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito in the province of Tucumán.

Keywords: Bacterial Nano Cellulose; Mosquito repellent; Topical formulation; Natural products

INTRODUCTION

Vegetal origin cellulose is traditionally obtained by polluting methods with strong acids, leaving a large amount of waste during the process. Nano scale is commonly obtain by the top-down enzymatic, mechanical and chemical treatments of cellulosic precursors. The most used precursors worldwide are cotton, wood, and annual plants. Other agricultural waste is also used such as sugar cane bagasse. That's the case of our province Tucuman-Argentina.^[1] In contrast, nanoscale cellulose can be obtained directly through a bottom-up approach, where it is biosynthesized for specific bacterial strains as bacterial nano cellulose (BNC).^[2] Bacterial species such as *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Gluconacetobacter xylinus*, *Gluconacetobacter hansenii* produce cellulose as one of their metabolites. *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* is the chosen study model by which biosynthetic mechanisms are carried out.^[3] The BNC production by *G. xylinus* is by construction of a nanofiber film at the air/culture medium interface.^[4,5] BNC is a primary metabolite synthesized inside the bacterial cell and then twisted into nanofibrils and mechanically amplified

to form microfibrils. ^[6,7] During the biosynthesis of cellulose chains, van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonds between hydroxyl groups and the oxygen from adjacent molecules promotes the parallel stacking of multiple cellulose chains that form elemental fibrils to aggregate into larger microfibrils. ^[8] BNC has distinctive characteristics due mainly to its size and fibrillar arrangement that introduces modifications in its biological and physicochemical properties such as biocompatibility and biodegradability. In addition, BNC fibers are lighter, have greater optical transparency, and their surface is chemically adaptable allowing the attachment of multiple functional groups and improving their mechanical properties. ^[9] BNC as a non active pharmaceutical ingredient, has a high water retention of up to 200 times its weight. ^[10,11] Its swelling capacity under special conditions makes it a unique model for the design of semi-solid topical pharmaceutical forms. ^[12] As COP28 is in sesión at this very moment, natural products and environmental awareness are at the crest of the wave. Excipients used for decades in pharmaceutical formulation are no longer in use. In particular, the focus is on remove from formulas petroleum derivatives. The new consumer seeks organic products, defined as those whose cultivation is free of agrochemicals, extraction is carried out in water or organic vegetable oils, and their synthetic excipients do not exceed the 5 % line. ^[13] All new care products such as mosquito repellent must meet these criteria, and also biodegradability and environmental sustainability. Abandoning or deminishing a selecting particular excipients such as petroleum derivatives and parabens is a part of the reviewing process. When reconsidering our old formulas, we have to incorporate concepts, such as the added value of a biodegradable natural sustainable product. This approach positions us in a comprehensive view of the formulation process and a new perspective of what well-being means. Cleaner production studies developed in our laboratory demonstrate that it is possible to reduce the concentration of excipients such as triethanol amine and carbopol in gels formulas with the addition of small concentrations of BNC. This work shows our experience in the redesign of the base formula for semi-solid gels, its implementation on a natural mosquito repellent manufacture in a joint experience with a rural school and community in our province. Amberes is a rural town located 70 km away from the capital of Tucuman province – Argentina (geographical coordinates:-27.267082, -65.488325). The secondary school students of the rural commune carried out an epidemiological survey for the most frequent problems in the area. The primary health care center (CAPS- Comuna de Amberes) provided alarming data regarding the prevalence of dengue virus, which is endemic in the area due to its geographical location close to Tucumán yungas and its high humidity percentages. As a project-based learning experience, researchers from National Council of Scientific and Technological Research (CONICET) and National University of Tucuman (UNT) worked together with the rural educational community to produce a natural mosquito repellent gel using local flora as an active ingredient and our gels with BNC as a vehicle. To the natural active pharmaceutical ingredient selection, aromatic plants from the area that contain citronellol and/or limonene in high concentrations were surveyed. *Cynbopogon citratus*, lemon grass or cedrón was selected for these trials, due to its abundance in the Amberes área. The premise that nature puts all solutions within our reach was taken as the fundamental axis of this joint work. The repellent currently marketed in Argentina is produced based on N,N-Diethyl-meta-toluamide (DEET). DEET is especially dangerous for young children, who may experience seizures when exposed to the chemical on their skin for long periods of time. ^[14] The safety evaluation and persistence studies of the repellent action were carried out on 100 healthy volunteers from Amberes commune.

The main objective of this work was to design a natural mosquito repellent, suitable for all ages, sustainable, biodegradable, that replaces commercial repellents based on DEET. To ensure the success of the technological design, quality controls established by the Argentine pharmacopeia and training for students and teachers of the rural school were carried out. In addition, the results of safety, organoleptic characteristics, acceptance and persistence of repellent action, were evaluated in 100 healthy volunteers from the community.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bacterial strains and culture conditions

A *Pseudomonas fluorescens* WS strain (wrinkly spreader) (donated by PhD Andrew Spears, School of Science, Engineering and Technology, Abertay University) It was grown in LB broth (Britania- C.A.B.A-Argentina) and kept at 25°C.

BNC production process

King B Media (Britania- C.A.B.A-Argentina). For BNC production, static cultivation was used. All growing test were made on petri dishes with 50 mL of fresh medium 72h at $28\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. All cellulose pellicles obtained were washing with distillate water to remove medium. BNC was centrifuged 20 min at 8000rpm. Then 1mL of NaOH 2% v/v was added and autoclaved 15min at 121°C , these procedure is made for detach some bacterial cell which could by immerse on BNC. Films were washed with distilled water until neutralization.^[15]

BNC dry weight

Dry weight was measured in dry films. The results were reported as 'production' and expressed in weight of dry cellulose per liter of King B medium (g/L).^[15]

Gel material

Carbomer 940, triethanolamine, (Fabriquimica-Buenos Aires, Argentina), sweet almond oil, cosgard type preservative, Cynbopogon citratus essential oil, (Eiffel Química-Buenos Aires Argentina) C. citratus hydroalcoholic extract common name in the area lemon grass.

Cynbopogon citratus extract preparation

The plant material was collected together with the students of the rural school in an organic cultivation field established in the Amberes comune (geographical coordinates:-27.256531,-65.510982). The hydroalcoholic extracts were prepared with the clean and dry plant material, and macerated in 50° alcohol according to the provisions of the Argentine Pharmacopoeia, seventh edition, for 15 days away from light and humidity. Then the macerated extract was filtered using low porosity cotton canvas and was reserved until use.

Formulation design^[16]

Formulation studies were carried out in order to evaluate pharmacotechnical aspects such as: pH, extensibility, viscosity, organoleptic properties, stability was developed as required on Administracion Nacional de Medicamentos, Alimentos y Tecnología Médica (ANMAT) disposition N°7667.

Homogeneity assays

Repelet gel designed was applied as a thin layer on polypropylene slides. The homogeneity was tested by visual appearance after application. The same formulation (3g) was used for centrifugation assays (15 min, 3500 rpm) and separation in phases was controlled¹⁷. Under these conditions the homogeneity of the repelet gel was qualitatively qualified as follows: very good (no phase separation), good (appearance of small volume of supernatant), regular (phase separation with slight appearance of clotted) and poor (separation of the phases with appearance of pellet).

pH measurements

The pH of repelet gel was measured in a pHmeter (Broadley James Corporation, Irvine, CA) by dipping the glass electrode into the gel. ^[16]

Rheological studies

The viscosity was determined and measured as centi Poise (cP) at 25 °C (stored temperature) and 32°C (healthy skin temperature) by using a Cannon viscometer with spindle N°8 from 3 rpm to 60 rpm (Cannon Instrument Company, LV2000 model, Pennsylvania, EEUU). ^[16,17]

Spreadability assays

The spreadability was evaluated using an extensometer consisted in two plates, the lower plate holds the sample (0.5 g) and the upper plate (28 g) exerts forces to the sample. ^[16] Force is generated by adding known weight in the upper plate (5 g) at pre-determinate times.

In vitro passive permeation studies^[18]

This assay was conducted using vertical type Franz diffusion cells having a receptor compartment capacity of 10 mL. Cellulose membranes (D9527 avg. flat width 43 mm (1.7 in.) Sigma Aldrich Chemical CO., St. Louis, MO) were mounted between the half-cells in contact with receptor fluid (0.9% NaCl) and were equilibrated for 1 h. The area available for diffusion was 1.8 cm². The fluid in the receptor compartment was maintained at 32 ± 0.5 °C (skin temperature). Semi-solid formulation (0.5 g) was placed in the donor compartment. The entire assembly was kept on a magnetic stirrer (100 rpm) and at each time four cells were removed from the system, aliquots (2 mL) of the receptor phase at specific time intervals (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 60 and 90 min). Limonene shows an absorbance peak at 207 nm due to isolated double bonds. The OD₂₀₇ of the solution was measured in a UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Spectronic Genesys 10 UV Rochester, NY). ^[19] Cumulative amounts of limonene on *Cymbopogon citratus* extract that permeated the diffusion unit surface (cm²) were plotted against time (min). The results were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD) (n=16).

Informed consent form development^[20]

Informed consent sheet was designed by the protocols approved for the World Health Organization^[20] and the provisions of the national regulatory entity National Administration of Drugs, Food and Medical Technology (ANMAT) N°6677/10. ^[21]

Safety, efficacy and persistence and organoleptic characteristics acceptance studies in healthy skin volunteers

Since there is no foreseeable risk from the use of BNC, nor other ingredient on the repellent designed is possible and representative to evaluate the safety of their ingredients simply evaluating the appearance of edema and/or erythema (exploring potential allergies) in clinical test. The corrosion test in a model of healthy skin was selected ^[22,23] as a validated methodology by ANMAT (Resolution N° 288/90) ^[24] in Argentina. This trial involved 100 healthy volunteers. The skin surface chosen was that recommended by the World Health Organization ^[20]. The guide for testing repellents on healthy volunteers suggests application to an extremity. An approximate surface of 75 cm², standard measurement of 5cmx15cm for men and women, was selected on the right arm back according to the average height of the area. For data collection, three dimensions were required: the length of the treatment area and proximal and distal limits of the treatment area.

For the safety studies, the following parameters were considered:

- a) absence of dermal reaction, nor edema, erythema or skin dryness
- b) weak reaction described as a slight presence of edema and/or erythema, skin dryness in the application area was considered.
- c) moderate reaction described as the presence of edema or erythema in the application area.

For the effectiveness and persistence studies, the following levels were considered:

- a) at least 3 hours
- b) between 2 and 3 hours
- c) between 1 and 2 hours

For the analysis of the results of the evaluation of organoleptic characteristics, the absorption speed perceived by the healthy volunteer was considered as:

- a) Fast absorption time as less than 5 minutes
- b) Medium absorption time as 5 to 10 min
- c) Slow absorption time 10 minutes or more

Other organoleptic characteristics achieved were those whose perceptions increase the user's comfort such as a pleasant aroma and refreshing sensation.

Ethical considerations

This study meets the ethical and scientists standards to design, conduct, recording and reporting studies that involve the participation of human beings stipulated by the Ministry of Health of Argentina, (Resolution N° 1490/07) ^[25]. They are based in the International Declarations of Human Rights and Ethics Research (Nuremberg, 1948) ^[26], Helsinki treated (1964 and updates of the World Medical Association) ^[27], the Operational Guidelines for Ethics Committees (WHO 2000 - World Health Organization) ^[28] and the International Ethical Guidelines for Health research Involving Human Subjects (CIOMS 2017 - Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences). ^[29]

Statistics

The t-test was used for statistical analysis. $p < 0.001$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

BNC dry weight

The BNC dry weight per liter of King B medium (g/L) was 11.95 ± 0.22 g/L. For the laboratory experience and studies in healthy volunteers, a total of 71.7g was prepared.

Formulation design

(Table 1) shows the mosquito repellent formulæ. Repellent gels have the benefit over creams due to their rapid absorption. In this design, specific climatic factors of the Yungas area of the province of Tucuman were considered. The high humidity in summer periods and strong winds along with the suspended dust due to the erosion generated by the large extensions of fields monocultured with sugar cane. A skin softening agent was incorporated sweet almond oil, and a natural preservative such as cosgard was used to replace parabens. ^[13]

Table 1. Mosquito repellent gel formulæ and composition.

Repellent gel formulæ in 100 g	
Carbomer	0,6 g
Triethanolamine	0,01 g
<i>Cymbonopogon citratus</i> extract	15 mL
Sweet almond oil	2 mL
<i>C. citratus</i> esencial oil	1 mL
Cosgard type preservative	0,2 mL
BNC	0,5 g
H ₂ O	e.q.f. 100 mL

Homogeneity assays

When the homogeneity studies were carried out, no presence of clusters, lumps or differences in the dispersion of the gel was observed. No phase separation was observed after centrifugation at 3500 rpm. The homogeneity of the repellent gel was categorized as very good and without phase separation.

pH measurements

When pH was measured, $\text{pH } 5.5 \pm 0.21$ was obtained. It was reported that these values are in the acceptable range for topical skin formulation in general. These values could variate from 4.0 - 6.2 depending on race, age, sex and environmental factors. ^[30] The importance of this parameter lies in the fact that acidic pH values of the skin surface regulate the homeostasis of the stratum corneum and the permeability of the skin barrier. This slightly acidic pH in the repellent formula favors the differentiation of keratinocytes, maintains the balance of normal skin microbial flora, stimulates the formation of epidermal lipids and the lipid envelope of corneocytes. The designed topical formulation is an extrinsic factor that has the added value of contributing to the maintenance of skin health. ^[31]

Rheological studies

The rheological assay showed that the semi-solid formulation designed, displayed thixotropic behavior. Viscosity measured $V_{25^{\circ}\text{C}}$ was $2262.2 \pm 3.9\text{cP}$ and $V_{32^{\circ}\text{C}}$ was $2231.1 \pm 4.2\text{cP}$. Rheological behavior in topical formulations is influenced by factors such as pH, temperature, polymer concentrations, polymer modification, polymer combinations. The incorporation of a combined polymers (carbomer and BNC) into the repellent formula designed creates a three-dimensional structure that improves the properties of the single linear polymer.^[32] A thixotropic behavior ensure uniform distribution and prolonged action of the incorporated active pharmaceutical ingredient on the topical sites.^[33]

In vitro passive permeation studies

The in vitro release study was performed. (Figure 1) shows the cumulative amount of Limonenne ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) during time (min) in all samples tested. The active pharmaceutical ingredient released reaches maximum concentration at 40 min. It is known that vehicles employed in formulations intended for topical use can greatly influence the rate and extent of drug permeation across the skin. In vitro skin permeation studies provide data on the degree of skin penetration of the active substance. The insect repellents have topical action and it is desired the retention of the active in the superficial layers of the skin and minimum permeation for the receptor solution of the in vitro permeation study. The in vitro passive permeation studies were performed primarily to verify concentration release from the carrier matrix as well as to predict time of application of treatment for human trials. Synthetic membranes are preferred to skin tissue as they are easier resourced, less expensive and structurally simpler^[34]. This means that large-scale studies can be undertaken more readily as well as the mechanisms can be deconvoluted^[35]. *Cymbopogon citratus* was selected due to its abundance in the area of the rural commune of Amberes. It is widely documented in the literature that the chemical composition of essential oils and extracts of plant origin vary dramatically, even within the same species. Sources of variability include the geographical origin of the plant, the part of the plant extracted, the phenological state of the plant and the time of year, as well as the environmental conditions of growth.^[36] Biological activity is also affected by interactions between its structural components. Bossou et. al showed that the composition of the essential oil and extracts of *Cymbopogon citratus* is much more homogeneous, with geranial as the main constituent regardless of the origin of the plant. Chemical composition of the essential oil and hydroalcoholic leaf extract of *C. citratus* revealed the order of concentrations of the main compounds geranial, limonene, β - myrcene, citronellal, limonene oxide, geraniol and linalool.^[37]

Figure 1. Cumulative amount of Limonene ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) during time (min) in all samples tested. The data shown represent the mean \pm SD of 16 replicates.

Safety studies in healthy skin volunteers

(Table 2) shows safety studies results for 100 healthy skin volunteers. The parameters evaluated were the possibility of allergies represented as the appearance of edema, erythema or a feeling of dryness on the skin of the volunteers surveyed. For a better interpretation of the results, the following categories were selected: a) Absence of dermal reaction, nor edema, erythema or skin dryness b) weak reaction described as a slight presence of edema and/or erythema, skin dryness in the application area was considered. c) moderate reaction described as the presence of edema or erythema in the application area. No allergies in the form of edema, erythema or dry skin were recorded. Previous studies carried out by other authors showed that: the use of BNC in pharmaceutical formulations presents non side effects or genotoxicity in vitro. [38] The absence of toxins from BNC nanofibers was demonstrated in vitro through cell viability and in flow cytometry assays on mouse cells in vivo. [39] BNC showed no adverse effects on cultured human umbilical vein endothelial cells, fibroblasts or chondrocytes. [40] In vitro analysis further reveals that 95% of mesenchymal stem cells accumulate in the cellulose membrane. [41] Furthermore, modified hydrophobic celluloses are GRAS materials widely used as excipients in the pharmaceutical industry. [42,43] This would explain the absence of undesirable effects in the designed mosquito repellent gel.

Table 2. Safety studies results for 100 healthy skin volunteers. **a) No reaction;** absence of dermal reaction, nor edema, erythema or skin dryness. **b) Weak reaction:** slight presence of edema and/or erythema, skin dryness in the application area. **c) Moderate reaction:** presence of edema or erythema in the application area.

Safety studies Description skin report			
Grade of skin reaction	n=100		p value
	0 h	24 h	
No reaction	100	100	<0.001
Weak reaction	0	0	<0.001
Moderate reaction	0	0	<0.001

Efficacy and persistence studies in healthy skin volunteers

(Figure 2) shows the results on effectiveness and persistence studies. An approximate surface of 75 cm², standard measurement of 5cmx15cm for men and women, was selected on the right arm back according to the average height of the area. For the effectiveness and persistence studies, the following levels were considered: a) at least 3 hours, b) between 2 and 3 hours, c) between 1 and 2 hours. In the survey carried out 24 hours after the application of the mosquito repellent in the 100 healthy volunteers surveyed, it was found that 62% of the volunteers perceived effectiveness and persistence of the product for 3 or more hours, 35% of those surveyed reported the persistence of the product between 2 and 3 hours after application and only 3% of the volunteers recorded persistences of less than 3%. These values are consistent with the commercial repellent currently used based on DEET, which in its form of administration suggests repeating the application approximately every 4 hours. ^[44] Additionally, in vitro studies revealed the release of limonene in a concentration of 2.7298 ± 0.2565 . These data confirm the effectiveness of the repellent action of the designed product. It is desirable that most of the active repellent ingredient remain on the surface of the skin. The variability in persistence could be due to factors such as skin type: oily, mixed or dry skin and genetic factors. Mosquitoes respond to human emanations with varying degrees of attraction. The attraction depends not only upon factors related to mosquito behavior, but also on the emanations produced by the host. Also attraction is influenced partly by bacteria present on the skin, diet, exercise. ^[45]

Figure 2. Effectiveness and persistence in skin results obtained 24 hours after the application of the mosquito repellent in the 100 healthy volunteers surveyed.

Organoleptic acceptance studies in healthy skin volunteers

(Figure 3) shows perceived skin absorption. For the results analysis on organoleptic characteristics, the absorption speed perceived by the healthy volunteer was considered as: a) fast absorption time as less than 5 minutes, b) medium absorption time as 5 to 10 min, c) slow absorption time 10 minutes or more. Other organoleptic characteristics achieved were those whose perceptions increase the user's comfort such as a pleasant aroma and refreshing sensation. Of 100% of the volunteers surveyed, 56% perceived rapid absorption of the product. 40% perceived absorption of the product in a period of between 5 and 10 minutes. This represents an advantage since it is an area with high humidity in summer periods and a high percentage of suspended dust. Quick drying is desirable since it increases the comfort level of the application and supplements the action of the commercial aerosol repellent without the need to increase the concentration of volatile excipients in the formula. The repellent natural gel was described as soft, with a pleasant aroma, rapid absorption and a persistent refreshing sensation.

Figure 3. Organoleptic characteristics analysis. Perceived absorption speed by the healthy volunteer was considered as: a) fast absorption time: less than 5 minutes, b) medium absorption time: 5 to 10 min, c) slow absorption time: 10 minutes or more.

CONCLUSIONS

The combined polymer formulation design introduced optimal characteristics in the natural mosquito repellent gel. The selection of the plant species met the desired characteristics of high concentration of terpenes from the limonene family and abundance in the study area. The pH values obtained are suitable for topically applied products and help to maintain skin health, contributing to the differentiation of keratinocytes, maintaining the balance of the skin microbiota, and stimulating the formation of protective lipids. The viscosity and extensibility tested *in vitro* are adequate, facilitating the application and persistence of the product on the skin. Studies in healthy volunteers showed absence of edema and erythema within 24 hours from application of the product. No perception of skin dryness was recorded among the 100 volunteers surveyed. The persistence of the product on the skin and the repellent action was at least 3 hours in 62% of the cases. The organoleptic properties were adequate. The gel was described as soft, with a pleasant aroma, rapid absorption and a persistent refreshing sensation. The product is suitable for use as a mosquito repellent, its design is optimal for the area where the study was carried out, due to its climatic characteristics and living conditions. It is desirable to continue the studies by expanding the number of healthy volunteers and the area of influence of the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito in the province of Tucuman.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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